

LINGUOPRAGMATIC AND LINGUOCULTURAL STUDY OF NON-LITERARY LEXICON IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7187640>

Abstract: Today, in linguistics, much attention is paid to the difference between Uzbek and English lexicon. The comparative research method is becoming especially important. In this article, we will give general information about linguopragmatic and linguocultural study of non-literary lexicon in English and Uzbek languages.

Keywords: linguopragmatics, linguoculturology, non-literary lexicon, dialects, professional lexicon, slang.

ЛИНГВОПРАГМАТИЧЕСКОЕ И ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРНОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ НЕЛИТЕРАТУРНОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация: сегодня в языкознании большое внимание уделяется разнице между узбекской и английской лексикой. Особое значение приобретает метод сравнительного исследования. В данной статье мы дадим общие сведения о лингвопрагматическом и лингвокультурологическом изучении нелитературной лексики в английском и узбекском языках.

Ключевые слова: лингвопрагматика, лингвокультурология, нелитературная лексика, диалекты, профессиональная лексика, сленг.

INTRODUCTION

Non-literary lexicon are divided into two groups in terms of their scope of use: the layer with unlimited scope of use and the layer with limited scope of use. Separation into such groups is mainly characteristic of lexemes in the categories of nouns, adjectives, adverbs and verbs. There are no restricted words in the categories of number and pronouns, as well as conjunctions, prepositions, and exclamations. [1, 43]

Lexemes with unlimited scope of use are words that are common to both English and Uzbek speakers, are understandable to everyone and are used equally in everyone's speech: hand, eyebrow, eye, tree, fruit (nouns); white, black, big, small, good, bad (adjectives); fast, little, many, deliberately, four (adjectives); walk, read, write (verbs) and others. Such lexemes are also called universal lexical units.

Lexemes with a limited scope of use are words characteristic of dialect, profession - craft lexeme, and jargon - slang. Non-literary used in live conversation are also limited lexical units. Most of the lexemes whose usage is not limited are common English and Uzbek words. However, at the same time, there are many differences among them. [3, 148]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Commonly used words in the English and Uzbek languages. Such words are widely used in everyday life, understandable for many people, and are characterized by their stylistic neutrality. The widely used words of both languages have not been studied enough. In some studies, this group of words was interpreted as a lexicon with an unlimited scope of use. In E. Begmatov's book "Lexical Layers of the Modern Uzbek Literary Language", the widely used words are divided into twenty-six different groups, each of which is explained with examples. Here are some of them: [2, 67]

names of things and phenomena related to natural existence: sun, moon, water, air, sky, star, river, mountain;

names of concepts representing various elements of nature: wind, storm, flood, lightning, lightning, flood, fog, earthquake;

words expressing movement and state, as well as human labor activity: walking, standing, hitting, running, running;

words related to the mental state of a person: joy, joy, joy, pity, cry;

names of people and animals: man, woman, boy, girl; horse, bird, dog, like;

names of human and animal parts and organs: head, foot, hand, finger, liver, lung, heart;

words related to relatives: father, mother, son, daughter, sister, child, uncle, grandfather, aunt, uncle, etc.;

words expressing the relationship between people, long closeness: dear, kind, caring, passionate, friend, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Words expressing the character and behavior of people and animals: agile, dexterous. Non-literary lexicon is the words used by all people living in a certain area, which are typical of the speech of the inhabitants of that area. In addition, the dialectal lexicon is unique to oral speech. In this respect, it is similar to a normal colloquial lexicon. However, the scope of application of ordinary colloquial lexicon will not be territorially limited. Dialectal words are not considered the lexicon of the literary language. "Dialecticism is a phenomenon characteristic not of a universal language, but of dialects that are local manifestations of this universal language; Accordingly, they are usually used in the speech of representatives of a dialect, and are often characteristic of representatives of other dialects, as well as literary language. [4, 98]

The style of speech is also characterized by the use of figurative words or small formative adverbs ("spoon", "book", "bread", "tea", "nice", "big", "little red"), defined words ("got up in the morning," "all ran"). Often it contains particles introductory words, ("Mary, go for bread!", "Oh, you came to us dear, there is a loving God!") from throwing a bite, blood circulation.

This method is characterized by the use of syntactically simple sentences, using complete sentence words, sentence (negative, positive, goals, etc.). This style is characterized by interruptions in speech, which can be caused by various reasons. [5, 4]

Non-literary words are an essential part of conversing in English and Uzbek. British slangs full of eccentric sayings and colloquialisms, which are useful in a wide variety of casual situations. Whether you're a beginner or a seasoned English speaker, you'll want to brush up on your command of slang terms and their meanings!

Now, you may be wondering what is a slang word, or what are some cool slang phrases? "Slang" refers to informal vocabulary words that aren't typically found in a dictionary. Many of these slang word shave multiple meanings, so you'll have to pay close attention to the context of a conversation in order to use them correctly. This makes it a good idea to practice your English and Uzbek slang words with friends before using them with strangers! [6, 2]

As you work your way through this list, keep in mind that English and Uzbek slang can vary depending on the region you are in. For example, certain slang words are more commonly used in rural areas versus in the inner city. You may find a different set of popular slang word son the West Coast of the US versus the East Coast or in the Midwest versus the Deep South. Not sure which ones to use in your area? Just spend a bit of time with the locals and hear what kind of slang they use! [2, 36]

1. What's up? – Hey; what are you doing?
“Hey Tom! What's up?”
“Not much!”
2. I feel you – I understand and empathize with you. Eg. “I feel you. That was really unfair.”
3. I get it – I understand. Eg. “I get it now! Thank you for explaining that.”
4. Same here – I agree.
“I'm having a hard time studying for this exam.”
“Same here.”
5. My bad – My mistake. Eg. “My bad! I didn't mean to do that.”
6. Oh my God! – (Used to describe excitement or surprise). Eg. “Oh my God! You scared me!”
7. You bet – Certainly; you're welcome.
“Thanks for the jacket, Tom!”
“You bet, Sally!”
8. No worries – That's alright. Eg. “No worries about the mess. I'll clean it up.”
9. No biggie – It's not a problem.
“Thanks for tutoring me, Tom!”
“No biggie, Sally.”
10. No big deal – (Same usage as above).
11. No sweat – (Same usage as above).
12. No problem – (Same usage as above).

CONCLUSIONS

Keep in mind that most popular phrases that are non-literary are meant for casual conversations, so you won't want to use these in a formal context. For so chances are you'll already be familiar with many of these words. Also, if you think these English and Uzbek words, they will work actually. There are a whole other world of English and Uzbek non-literary phrases out there. While there may be a few crossover phrases, by and large, the countries have their own unique sets of lexicon. In conclusion, in general, lexemes with a limited scope include dialects, words related to professional lexicon, slang, vulgarisms, terms.

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